

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART XI. SOME AZO DYES OF ETHYLENE-BIS-N¹-SULPHANILAMIDE*

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Aromatic amino-azo dyes and aromatic hydroxy-azo dyes of ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide have been prepared by coupling tetrazotised ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide with various aromatic hydroxy compounds and aromatic amines.

Gley and Girard (*Presse. Med.*, 1936, 42, 1775; cf. Rajagopalan, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 19A, 351) made the interesting observation that inspite of the molecular amounts of prontosil and sulphanilamide being equal in activity against streptococcal infection, the carboxy derivatives of prontosil were twice as active although it could liberate no more sulphanilamide than the previous drug *in vivo*.

Considering the encouraging activity of azo dyes of sulpha-family, especially prontosil (Domagk, *Deut. Med. Wochschr.*, 1935, 61, 250,) and rubiazol (Levaditi and Vaisman *Compt. rend.*, 1935, 200, 1694) and those obtained from N¹-alkylsulphanilamides (Lydia and Aldo, *Gazzetta*, 1940, 70, 369) it was thought worthwhile to prepare some important azo derivatives of ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (Bami, Iyer and Guha, *Science & Culture*, 1945, 11, 269).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide has been tetrazotised and coupled with two molecular proportions of various aromatic hydroxy compounds to give the azo dyes of type A from (I—X).

(R = coupling agent mentioned after each compound less one hydrogen)

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| (I) R = phenol | (VI) R = resorcinol |
| (II) R = <i>p</i> -cresol | (VII) R = resorcinol ethyl ether |
| (III) R = 1:2:5-xylenol | (VIII) R = resorcinol methyl ether |
| (IV) R = <i>o</i> -nitrophenol | (IX) R = α -naphthol |
| (V) R = salicylic acid | (X) R = β -naphthol |

The tetrazonium salt of ethylene-bis-sulphanilamide has been reacted with two molecular proportions of various aromatic amines to give the azo dyes of type A from (XI—XX).

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| (XI) R = aniline | (XVI) R = <i>p</i> -anisidine |
| (XII) R = <i>p</i> -toluidine | (XVII) R = anthranilic acid |
| (XIII) R = 1:3:6-xylidene | (XVIII) R = <i>m</i> -phenylenediamine |
| (XIV) R = dimethylaniline | (XIX) R = β -naphthylamine |
| (XV) R = <i>m</i> -aminophenol | (XX) R = naphthionic acid |

* A preliminary note of this work has been published in *Science & culture* 1946, 12, 153.

All these dyes are coloured, amorphous powders with shades varying from light red to dark brown. They cannot be crystallised and they usually decompose on melting.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(4-hydroxybenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (I).— *Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide* (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 3 c.c.). The solution was cooled to 0° and sodium nitrite solution (10%, 4 c.c.) was added to it. Hydrochloric acid (10%, 5 c.c.) was then added drop by drop with stirring and the reaction mixture allowed to stand for half-an-hour when the diazonium salt was obtained as a light yellow precipitate.

The above mixture was added to phenol (0.6 g.), dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 10 c.c.), cooled at 0°, when a red solution of the sodium salt of the dye was obtained. After 2 hours the dye was precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered and washed well with cold water. The product could not be crystallised from usual organic solvents and hence it was purified from the dilute alkali solution by precipitation with acid after stirring with norit in cold. The product was filtered, washed and dried and obtained as a reddish amorphous powder, m.p. 175° (decomp.), yield 1.4 g. (Found: N, 13.91. $C_{26}H_{24}O_6N_6S_2$ requires N, 14.52 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2-hydroxy 5-methylbenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (II).— *Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide* (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with *p*-cresol (0.6 g.) in excess of sodium hydroxide at 0° as described under (I). Finally, a red powder was obtained, m.p. 150° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 13.73. $C_{28}H_{26}O_6N_6S_2$ requires N, 13.81 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2:5-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (III). — *Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide* (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with 1:2:5-xylenol (0.7 g.) as described under (I). The purified product was obtained as a red powder, m.p. 172° (decomp.), yield 1.6 g. (Found: N, 12.95. $C_{30}H_{30}O_6N_6S_2$ requires N, 13.20 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(3-nitro-4-hydroxybenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (IV).— *Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide* (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with *o*-nitrophenol (0.8 g.) as described under (I). The product was obtained as a reddish yellow powder, m.p. 171° (decomp.), yield 1.6 g. (Found: N, 16.03. $C_{26}H_{22}O_{10}N_6S_2$ requires N, 16.73 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(4-hydroxy-5-carboxylic-benzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (V).— *Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide* (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with salicylic acid (0.8 g.) and the product obtained as under (I) as a light brown powder, m.p. 236° (decomp.), yield 1.6 g. (Found: N, 12.21. $C_{28}H_{22}O_{10}N_6S_2$ requires N, 12.56 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2:4-dihydroxybenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (VI).— *Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide* (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with resorcinol (0.6 g.) as under (I). Finally the product was obtained as a brown powder with no definite decomposition point, yield 1.6 g. (Found: N, 13.4. $C_{28}H_{24}O_8N_6S_2$ requires N, 13.72 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2-ethoxy-4-hydroxybenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (VII).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with resorcinol monoethyl ether (0.8 g.) as under (I). The product was isolated and purified as before and obtained as a dark red powder, m.p. 145° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 12.1. C₂₀H₂₂O₆N₂S₂ requires N, 12.57 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2-methoxy-4-hydroxybenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (VIII).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with resorcinol monoethyl ether (0.7 g.) and the product obtained as a dark red dye, m.p. 192° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 13.58. C₁₈H₂₀O₆N₂S₂ requires N, 13.12 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(1-hydroxynaphthylazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (IX).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) and α -naphthol (0.8 g.) were coupled together and the product obtained as a brown powder, m.p. 152° (decomp.), yield 1.8 g. (Found: N, 11.99. C₂₄H₂₀O₆N₂S₂ requires N, 12.42 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2-hydroxynaphthyl-3-azophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (X).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide and β -naphthol were coupled together in quantities and manner as detailed under (IX) when a red powder, m.p. 258° (decomp.), was obtained, yield 1.7 g. (Found: N, 12.0; S, 9.6. C₂₄H₂₀O₆N₂S₂ requires N, 12.42; S, 9.41 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(4-aminobenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XI).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised as described under (I) and coupled with aniline (0.5 g.), dissolved in hydrochloric acid (10%, 3 c.c.) at 0°. Sodium acetate (7 g.) in water (15 c.c.) was then added to remove the mineral acid in excess, and the mixture kept overnight. The red precipitate that had separated was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and finally dried. The product could not be crystallised from usual organic solvents and obtained as a red powder, m.p. 185° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 18.88; S, 10.7. C₂₀H₂₂O₄N₂S₂ requires N, 19.37; S, 11.07 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(5-methyl-2-aminobenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XII).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with *p*-toluidine (0.6 g.) as under (XI). It was finally obtained as a brick-red powder decomposing above 135°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 18.95. C₂₀H₂₀O₄N₂S₂ requires N, 19.24 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2-amino-5 : 6-dimethylbenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XIII).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with *p*-xylydine (0.6 g.) as under (XI) to give a brick-red dye, m.p. 138° (decomp.), yield 1.6 g. (Found: N, 17.25. C₂₀H₂₄O₄N₂S₂ requires N, 17.66 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(4-dimethylaminobenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XIV).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with dimethylaniline (0.7 g.) to give an orange-red powder as under (XI), m. p. 253° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 17.34. C₂₀H₂₄O₄N₂S₂ requires N, 17.66 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2-amino-4-hydroxybenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XV).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with *m*-aminophenol (0.6 g.) as under (XI) to give a reddish yellow powder, m.p. 176° (decomp.), yield 1.4 g. (Found: N, 17.65. C₂₂H₂₀O₆N₂S₂ requires N, 18.36 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(5-methoxy-2-aminobenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XVI).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with *p*-anisidine (0.7 g.)

to give a reddish yellow powder as under (XI), m.p. 140° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (Found : N, 17.1. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 17.55 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(3-carboxylic-4-aminobenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XVII).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with anthranilic acid (0.75 g.) as in (XI). A yellow powder was obtained, m.p. 10° (decomp.), yield 1.7 g. (Found : N, 16.25. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 16.81 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2:4-diaminobenzeneazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XVIII).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with phenylenediamine hydrochloride (1 g.) in water (5 c.c.) as in (XI) to yield a brown powder, m. p. 223° (decomp.), yield 1.7 g. (Found : N, 22.60. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_6S_2$ requires N, 23.02 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(2-aminonaphthylazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XIX).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with β -naphthylamine (0.8 g.) as in (XI). The product was obtained as a red powder, m.p. 210° (decomp.), yield 1.7 g. (Found : N, 16.09. $C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 16.15 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(1-amino-4-sulphonic-naphthylazophenyl-p-sulphonamide) (XX).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) was tetrazotised and coupled with naphthionic acid (1.1 g.) as in (XI) to give a dark red powder decomposing above 250°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : N, 12.92. $C_{22}H_{20}O_6N_4S_4$ requires N, 13.36 per cent).

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Received July 10, 1948.